

3rd Workshop HPC-TRES

OGS Report: 2021/36 Sez. OCE 14 ECHO

December 11th, 2020 - Trieste, Italy

HPC-TRES website: <http://www.ogs.trieste.it/en/content/hpc-training-and-research-earth-sciences-hpc-tres>

OGS

National Institute
of Oceanography
and Applied
Geophysics

www.ogs.trieste.it

www.cineca.it

Edited by: S. Salon, M. Zanenghi, V. Mosetti
Trieste, April 2021

HPC-TRES program, web page:

<http://www.ogs.trieste.it/en/content/hpc-training-and-research-earth-sciences-hpc-tres>

Cover: snapshot taken during the virtual meeting with some participants.

3rd Workshop HPC-TRES

High Performance Computing – Training and Research for Earth Sciences

December 11th 2020, Virtual Meeting

The HPC-TRES program

HPC-TRES is a national initiative promoted by OGS and CINECA aimed to implement a training program focused on High Performance Computing (HPC) applications for Earth Sciences. HPC-TRES is co-sponsored by the Minister of University and Research (MUR) under its extraordinary contribute for the Italian participation to activities related to the international infrastructure PRACE – The Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe.

The major objectives of the program are: capacity building, enhancement of human resources, and advanced training in the fields of Earth System modelling (atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere and biosphere) and numerical models, the latter considered as a strategic cross-cutting element for modelling activities. These objectives are pursued through the use of national and European HPC infrastructures and services in the framework of PRACE, the optimization of algorithms and numerical codes, the optimal management of “Earth Sciences Big Data”, and the graphical visualization techniques for multidisciplinary applications in the Earth Sciences, also in the frame of the “Blue Growth” strategy.

Therefore, the HPC-TRES program establishes, sponsors and oversees training and research awards (in the form of scholarships grants) that support the research lines described in the scientific plan of the HPC-TRES program. A number of Italian research groups and institutions involved in HPC applications for Earth Sciences (INGV-Pisa, CNR/ISAC, CNR/IGG, CMCC, ICTP-ESP, MOX-Politecnico di Milano, ENEA-SSPT, INGV-SST, INGV-CNT, Univ. Bicocca, CRS4, EURAC, ARPA-FVG, Fondazione CIMA, Univ. Genova, Univ. Trieste, Consorzio LAMMA) have already endorsed the HPC-TRES initiative, contributing to the HPC-TRES scientific plan.

The 3rd HPC-TRES workshop

The 3rd workshop of HPC-TRES was organized by OGS as a virtual meeting, due to the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 emergency. The main objectives were: to share a common discussion with all the research groups that contribute to the HPC-TRES scientific plan, to present the status and the current outcomes of the research activities, to highlight the future perspectives of the national HPC infrastructure and to offer an opportunity of cross-discipline contamination, supported by the common HPC background which characterizes the different scientific approaches adopted by the research groups involved in the program.

A total of 48 attendees participated to the workshop, with 28 past and present HPC-TRES grantees (62% of the total grants acknowledged by the program in the period 2014-2020). Among them, 24 presented the main results of their research work, highlighting the scientific and technological challenges they have coped with. Modelling studies at different spatial and temporal scales, implementation of innovative algorithms, model optimization, HPC model data management, covered different Earth Sciences topics: from global to regional climate, atmosphere, ocean, hydrology, volcanic and earthquakes studies. Moreover, Mirko Cestari and Simone Bna’ from CINECA also gave their contribute with two opening talks, the first about the new pre-exascale facility Leonardo, the second focused on the use of GPU.

Tab. 1 shows the list of participants, some information related to the reference HPC-TRES research line where they are involved, and the title of the presentations. The abstracts of the presentations are included in the present report.

	Name, institution	Notes (role, research line, title of presentation)
1	Giovanni Aloisio, CMCC	Steering Committee (E1)
2	Giorgio Amati, CINECA	
3	Enrico Baglione, INGV	The 2nd May 2020 Crete earthquake and the induced tsunami (B9)
4	Julie Baron, OGS	3D numerical modeling of site-city interaction (B1)
5	Giacomo Bertoldi, EURAC	(C7)
6	Endalkachew Bogale Gelaw, CIMA	Coupling of Atmospheric and Hydrological Modelling (D7)
7	Giorgio Bolzon, OGS	(A1)
8	Simone Bna', CINECA	Toward Performance-Portable OpenFOAM for GPU-based Exascale Systems (invited)
9	Federico Brogi, INGV	Mixed precision in OpenFOAM (invited)
10	Stefano Campanella, OGS/EURAC	An empirical study on the calibration of the GEOtop model using supercomputers (C7)
11	Mattia Carello, OGS/UNIBO/CRS4	An HPC case study: Reverse Time Migration (B10)
12	Mirko Cestari, CINECA	Meet Leonardo, HPC pre-exascale for earth science
13	Gianluca Coidessa, OGS	Parallelizing OGSTM - BFM I/O (A1)
14	Nicola Creati, OGS	(B4)
15	Alessandro D'Anca, CMCC	(E1)
16	Eleonora Denich, UNITS/OGS	Electromagnetic inversion under the Low Induction Number (LIN) approximation (B3)
17	Marco De Pasquale, ESTECO	(A2)
18	Fabien Desbiolles, Univ. Bicocca	Role of Ocean Mesoscale variability on low-level atmospheric dynamics, cloud cover and Rainfall (D5)
19	Valeria Di Biagio, OGS	Extreme event waves in marine ecosystems (C3, D1)
20	Donatello Elia, CMCC	(E1)
21	Tomaso Esposti Ongaro, INGV	Steering Committee (B5, B6, B7, C4)
22	Matilde García-Valdecasas Ojeda, ICTP/OGS	Climate change impact on flood hazards over Italy (C6)
23	Andrea Giannotta, CMCC	Portable climate data analytics at scale through software containers (E1)
24	Mostafa Hamouda, Univ. Bicocca	European Extreme Precipitation: the effects of spatio-temporal resolution of the data (D5)
25	Francesco Immorlano, Univ. Salento	Machine Learning for Climate Change applications (E1)
26	Peter Klin, OGS	(B1, B2)
27	Piero Lanucara, CINECA	
28	Célia Laurent, OGS	HPC implementations in the SHYFEM hydrodynamic model using the PETSc library and application to modern architectures (A3, A4)
29	Andrea Magrin, OGS	(B15)
30	Arnau Mirò, OGS	Scientific visualization and machine learning (A1)
31	Chiara Montagna, INGV	(B6)

32	Manuel Musio, CMCC	High-throughput task management for climate analysis workflows (E1)
33	Lyuba Novi, CNR-IGG	A complex networks approach to marine connectivity through sea surface temperature (invited)
34	Stella Paronuzzi Ticco, BSC	Mixed precision implementation in a SL-DG model (invited)
35	Eric Pascolo, CINECA	(A1, A4)
36	Claudia Pasquero, Univ. Bicocca	(D5)
37	Giovanni Petris, UNITS/OGS	A three-dimensional numerical model for the noise propagation in an inhomogeneous medium (A7)
38	Bojana Petrovic, OGS	(B13)
39	Alessio Piatanesi, INGV	(B9)
40	Gloria Pietropoli, UNITS/OGS	(A1)
41	Marco Reale, OGS	Biogeochemical dynamics of the Mediterranean Sea in the future climate scenarios (D3)
42	Giorgia Rosset, UNITS/OGS	Gas hydrate behaviour in natural reservoir (E6)
43	Stefano Salon, OGS	Steering Committee, Secretary (A1, A2, D1)
44	Chiara Scaini, OGS	(B12)
45	Lavinia Tunini, OGS	Automatic GPS data processing on Galileo machine (B15)
46	Aldo Vesnaver, OGS	(B3)
47	Jost von Hardenberg, Politecnico Torino	Steering Committee (D2)
48	Luigi Sante Zampa, UNITS/OGS	Evaluation of topographic effects on land and marine gravity data: a case study of the Gulf of Manfredonia and the North Adriatic region (B11)
49	Maria Zanenghi, OGS	Logistic Support

Tab. 1 – List of participants (with affiliations), and notes including role, HPC-TRES research lines (if present), and title of presentation.

Acknowledgements

The 3rd HPC-TRES workshop was supported by OGS thanks to the MUR grant “PRACE-Italy”, under the extraordinary contribute for the Italian participation to activities related to the international infrastructure PRACE – The Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe.

We acknowledge Maria Zanenghi and William Toson (OGS) for the logistic support in the organization of the virtual meeting.

The HPC-TRES Steering Committee:
 Cosimo Solidoro (OGS, Trieste)
 Filippo Giorgi (ICTP, Trieste)
 Tomaso Esposti Ongaro (INGV, Pisa)
 Antonello Provenzale (CNR-IGG, Pisa)
 Giovanni Aloisio (Univ. Salento e CMCC, Lecce)
 Jost von Hardenberg (Politecnico di Torino)
 Eric Pascolo (CINECA, Bologna)
 Stefano Salon (OGS, Trieste)

Index

Page	Author	Title
7	Baglione, E.	The 2nd May 2020 Crete earthquake and the induced tsunامي
9	Baron, J.	3D numerical modeling of site-city interaction
11	Bna', S.	Toward Performance-Portable OpenFOAM for GPU-based Exascale Systems
13	Bogale Gelaw, E.	Coupling of Atmospheric and Hydrological Modelling
15	Campanella, S.	An empirical study on the calibration of the GEOtop model using supercomputers
17	Carello, M.	An HPC case study: Reverse Time Migration
19	Coidessa, G.	Parallelizing OGSTM - BFM I/O
21	Denich, E.	Electromagnetic inversion under the Low Induction Number (LIN) approximation
23	Desbiolles, F.	Role of Ocean Mesoscale variability on low-level atmospheric dynamics, cloud cover and Rainfall
25	Di Biagio, V.	Extreme event waves in marine ecosystems
27	Garcia-Valdecasas, M.	Climate change impact on flood hazards over Italy
29	Giannotta, A.	Portable climate data analytics at scale through software containers
31	Hamouda, M.	European Extreme Precipitation: the effects of spatio-temporal resolution of the data
33	Immorlano, F.	Machine Learning for Climate Change applications
35	Laurent, C.	HPC implementations in the SHYFEM hydrodynamic model using the PETSc library and application to modern architectures
37	Mirò, A.	Scientific visualisation and machine learning (experiences from HPC-TRES)
39	Musio, M.	High-throughput task management for climate analysis workflows
41	Paronuzzi Ticco, S.	Mixed precision implementation in a SL-DG model
43	Petris, G.	A three-dimensional numerical model for the noise propagation in an inhomogeneous medium
45	Reale, M.	Biogeochemical dynamics of the Mediterranean Sea in the future climate scenarios
47	Tunini, L.	Automatic GPS data processing on Galileo machine
49	Zampa, L. S.	Evaluation of topographic effects on land and marine gravity data: a case study of the Gulf of Manfredonia and the North Adriatic region

The 2 May 2020 Earthquake (Mw 6.6) and the induced Tsunami

Baglione, E.^{1,2}, Amato, A.², Brizuela, B.², Firat, B.², Lorito, S.², Piatanesi, A.², Romano, F.², Tonini, R.², Volpe, M.²

¹National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Trieste, Italy

²National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology INGV, Roma, Italy

Keywords: earthquake, tsunami, early warning, seismic source, tsunami hazard

On 2 May 2020 at 12:51:07 UTC, a moment magnitude (Mw) 6.6 earthquake occurred in the middle of the Hellenic subduction zone (HSZ). The earthquake occurred offshore, about 80 km south of Crete, generating a small local tsunami recorded by the Ierapetra tide gauge, on the southern coast of Crete island.

We present a seismic source solution for the earthquake. We used this single marigram data to constrain the main features of the causative rupture. Scanning systematically the source's parameters between limit values we performed synthetic tsunami waveforms and retrieved the best earthquake's characteristics through the comparison with the observed data. The use of the single marigram revealed to be efficient and able to well constrain the on-fault slip and the main focal mechanism of the source. Our results identify a shallow highly dipping thrusting fault, 11.5 km deep, characterized by an average slip of 0.5 m. This determination is in agreement with the recurring ruptures along that portion of the Hellenic subduction zone and the tsunamigenic potential of such events.

The enrichment in the characterization of such a seismic area plays a key role in understanding the ruptures that can more easily occur and in the perspective of a tsunami early warning system.

Fig.1 – Fig.1 – Maximum water elevation field of the simulated tsunami for the 2 May 2020 earthquake.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-01.

3D modelling of seismic site-city interaction

Baron, J., Petrovic, B., Klin, P.

National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: ground motion, soil-structure interaction, 3D numerical modelling

Seismic site effects, such as stratigraphic or topographic effects, can have a high impact on the ground motion registered at the surface. The latter can be further modified by Soil-Structure Interaction (SSI) that reflects the potential of a structure to modify the soil response and vice versa. At urban scale, the multiplication of these interactions and its coupling to site effect amplification is referred as Site-City Interactions (SCI). Understanding better these interactions and how they contribute to variations of ground shaking over short distances, will make it possible in the long term to identify areas of higher seismic risk within urban areas and to include these effects into best practice and contribute to guidelines for standard risk assessment and mitigation approaches.

Up to now, studies based on 2D and 3D numerical modelling investigated the theoretical possibility of SSI and SCI with simplified configurations, without the possibility of a comparison between the predicted and the observed seismic waves [1]. However, recent advances in seismic instrumentation and the increase in the available computational power, allow now performing adequate experiments to investigate the SSI and SCI phenomena by both real data analysis and numerical simulations [2]. In this context, the USCINT (Improving the understanding of Site-City Interactions for better earthquake risk mitigation) research project includes an ad hoc seismic experiment alongside with the analysis of both empirical data and numerical modelling. Empirical data, from seismic noise and active sources, have been collected on a test site in Ferrara (northern Italy) during a two days campaign in the frame of the CLARA project [3]. The 300m x 300m area of interest cover an athletic ground next to a building complex made of three identical 17m high RC structures.

We perform numerical simulations with the SPECFEM3D open-source software [4], based on the spectral element method, using the computational hours granted through an ISCRA-C project on the GALILEO machine of CINECA HPC centre. In particular, we aim at:

- modelling the seismic response of the test site for an incoming seismic wave.
- validating the test site model with a comparison between the numerical results and the empirical observations at the test site.
- extending 3D numerical modelling to different building configurations.

We expect that the numerical results would allow us to highlight the possible interference effects in the seismic field scattered by the buildings and to quantify the aggravation of the seismic hazard due to these effects.

We present here the first step of this analysis, consisting of the design of the computational mesh, performed with the internal mesher of the SPECFEM3D software (FIG.1). The computational grid is enlarged to 3km to avoid effects from source geometry and includes a 1D velocity model, attenuation, and Perfectly Match Layer boundary condition. To reach a 12Hz resolution and comply with the buildings' dimension, the minimum spectral element size is set to 4m.

Fig.1 – Zoom on the Spectral element computational grid, built with the internal mesher of the SPECFEM3D software for the area of interest. 1D velocity model, attenuation and PML boundary conditions are included in the mesh.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2017-22. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high-performance computing resources and support (IscraC “3DSSISCI”). Bojana Petrovic is supported by a research fellowship from the German Research Foundation (DFG, PE 2891/1-1).

References

- [1] Wirgin, A. and Bard, P.-Y., 1996, Effects of building on the duration and amplitude of ground motion in Mexico City. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*. 86. 914-920
- [2] Guéguen P., Colombi A., 2016, Experimental and Numerical Evidence of the Clustering Effect of Structures on Their Response during an Earthquake: A Case Study of Three Identical Towers in the City of Grenoble, France. *Bull. Seism. Soc. Am* , 106 (6): 2855–2864.
- [3] Petrovic B., Parolai S., Romanelli M., Affatato A., Petronio L., Barbagallo A., Sorgo D., Stefani M. and Caputo R., 2019, Un approccio innovativo per una migliore comprensione dell'interazione sismica tra suolo e strutture: il test site di Ferrara. *Boll. di Geofisica Teorica ed Applicata*. Vol. 60. 140-147.
- [4] Peter D., Komatitsch D., Luo Y., Martin R., Le Goff N., Casarotti E., Le Loher P., Magnoni F., Liu Q., Blitz C., Nissen-Meyer T., Basini P., and Tromp J., 2011, Forward and adjoint simulations of seismic wave propagation on fully hexahedral meshes, *Geophysical Journal International*, 186, 721-739, doi:10.1111/j.1365-246X.2011.05044.x

Toward Performance-Portable OpenFOAM for GPU-based Exascale Systems

Bna', S.¹, Spisso, I.¹, Zampini, S.²

¹CINECA, Bologna, Italy

²King Abdullah University of Science and Technology - KAUST, Saudi Arabia

Keywords: OpenFOAM, PETSc library, GPU

The current work is a preliminary comparison between the native multigrid solver embedded in the OpenFOAM package and the multigrid linear solver provided by the PETSc library, available in OpenFOAM thanks to the Petsc4FOAM library, with and without GPU support. Regarding the GPU implementation, the viennaCL, kokkos and cusparse formats are used in this study. Caching of the converted matrix and its preconditioner is also investigated. Software comparisons have been done on two different architectures (Intel Skylake and IBM Power9 + NVIDIA V100) on a single node. Preliminary results indicate good speed-up when the GPUs are not oversubscribed.

Coupling of Atmospheric and Hydrological Modelling

Bogale Gelaw, E.^{1,2}, Ferraris, L.², Parodi, A.², Delogu, F.², Gabellani, S.²

¹CIMA Research Foundation, Savona, Italy

²Department of Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics and Systems Engineering (DIBRIS) - University of Genoa, Genoa, Italy

Keywords: hydroinformatics, hydrological modeling, atmospheric simulation, parallel computing, model coupling

To exploit the computation power of high-performance computing machines for distributed hydrological modeling, the serial version of the Hydrological Model Continuum (HMC for short) (Silvestro et al., 2013) will be changed into parallel using the Message Passing Interface (MPI) (Walker, 1994) parallel programming paradigm. Because hydrological problems are mainly domain-decomposition type of problems, the Zoltan library (Catalyurek et al., 2007) is used to solve the load imbalance that is expected during the partitioning of the entire computational domain to the available compute cores of the machine.

To address the problems in model structure and data uncertainty, an intelligent coupling of hydrological and atmospheric modeling systems is regarded as the best approach (Sorooshian et al., 2008). To accomplish that the parallelized version of HMC will be fully coupled with the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) (Skamarock et al., 2019) atmospheric model. As the two candidate models are written in Fortran and parallelized for distributed memory computers the coupling interface will be developed using Fortran. However, since model coupling by itself is very complex task, the OASIS-MCT standard model coupling framework (Craig et al., 2017) will be used to assist the coupling process.

Finally, the resulting coupled model will be tested for its performance and scalability with a case study watershed in Italy. Then it will be packaged and deployed for ease of access and to be use by different user groups.

Acknowledgement

The research is supported by OGS under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-08.

References

Silvestro, F., Gabellani, S., Delogu, F., Rudari, R., & Boni, G. (2013). Exploiting remote sensing land surface temperature in distributed hydrological modelling: the example of the Continuum model. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 17(1), 39.

Walker, D. W. (1994). The design of a standard message passing interface for distributed memory concurrent computers. *Parallel Computing*, 20(4), 657-673.

Catalyurek, U. V., Boman, E. G., Devine, K. D., Bozdog, D., Heaphy, R., & Riesen, L. A. (2007, March). Hypergraph-based dynamic load balancing for adaptive scientific computations. In 2007 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium (pp. 1-11). IEEE.

Sorooshian, S., Hsu, K. L., Coppola, E., Tomassetti, B., Verdecchia, M., & Visconti, G. (Eds.). (2008). *Hydrological modelling and the water cycle: coupling the atmospheric and hydrological models* (Vol. 63). Springer Science & Business Media.

Skamarock, C., Klemp, B., Dudhia, J., Gill, O., Liu, Z., Berner, J., Wang, W., Powers, G., Duda, G., Barker, D., Huang, X., 2019. A Description of the Advanced Research WRF Model Version 4. <https://doi.org/10.5065/1dfh-6p97>

Craig, A., Valcke, S., & Coquart, L. (2017). Development and performance of a new version of the OASIS coupler, OASIS3-MCT_3.0. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 10(9).

An empirical study on the the GEOTop model calibration using supercomputers

Campanella, S.^{1,2}, Bertoldi, G.¹, and Sartori, A.³

¹Eurac Research, Institute for Alpine Environment, Bolzano, Italy

²National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics – OGS, Trieste, Italy

³SISSA, Trieste, Italy.

Keywords: hydrology, model calibration, black-box optimization, high performance computing

Proper characterization of uncertainty remains a major research and operational challenge in Earth and Environmental Systems Models (EESMs). In fact, model calibration is often more an art than a science: one must make several discretionary choices, guided more by his own experience and intuition than by the scientific method. In practice, this means that the result of calibration (CA) could be suboptimal. One of the challenges of CA is the large number of parameters involved in EESM, which hence are usually selected with the help of a preliminary sensitivity analysis (SA). Finally, the computational burden of EESMs models and the large volume of the search space make SA and CA very time-consuming processes.

This work applies a modern HPC approach to optimize a complex, over parameterized hydrological model, improving the computational efficiency of SA/CA. We apply the derivative-free optimization algorithms implemented in the Facebook Nevergrad Python library (Rapin and Teytaud, 2018) on a HPC cluster, thanks to the Dask framework (Dask Development Team, 2016).

The approach has been applied to the GEOTop hydrological model (Rigon et al., 2006; Endrizzi et al., 2014) to predict the time evolution of variables as soil water content and evapotranspiration for several mountain agricultural sites in South Tyrol with different elevation, land cover (pasture, meadow, orchard), and soil types.

We performed simulations on one-dimensional domains, where the model solves the energy and water budget equations in a column of soil and neglects the lateral water fluxes. Even neglecting the distribution of parameters across layers of soil, considering a homogeneous column, one has tens of parameters, controlling soil and vegetation properties, where only a few of them are experimentally available.

Because the interpretation of global SA could be difficult or misleading and the number of model evaluations needed by SA is comparable with CA, we employed the following strategy. We performed CA using all the continuous parameters and SA after CA, using the samples collected during CA, to interpret the results. However, given the above mentioned computational challenges, this strategy is possible only using HPC resources. For this reason, we focused on the computational aspects of calibration from an HPC perspective and examined the scaling of these algorithms and their implementation up to 1024 cores on a cluster. Other issues that we had to address were the complex shape of the search space and robustness of CA and SA against model convergence failure.

The use of HPC resources and techniques allows calibrating models with a high number of parameters within a reasonable computing time and exploring the parameters space properly. This is particularly important with noisy, multimodal objective functions. In our case, it revealed itself essential to determine the parameters controlling the water retention curve, which is highly not linear. The developed framework, which is published and freely available on GitHub, shows also how libraries and tools used within the machine learning community could be useful and easily adapted to EESMs CA.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by Eurac Research, OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-33.

References

Rigon, R., Bertoldi, G., & Over, T. M. (2006). GEOTop: A Distributed Hydrological Model with Coupled Water and Energy Budgets. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, 7, 371–388.

Endrizzi, S., Gruber, S., Dall’Amico, M. & Rigon, R. GEOTop 2.0: simulating the combined energy and water balance at and below the land surface accounting for soil freezing, snow cover and terrain effects. *Geosci Model Dev* 7, 2831–2857 (2014).

J. Rapin and O. Teytaud (2018). Nevergrad - A gradient-free optimization platform. <https://github.com/facebookresearch/nevergrad>

Dask Development Team (2016). Dask: Library for dynamic task scheduling. <https://dask.org>

An HPC case study: Reverse Time Migration

Carello, M.¹, Theis, D.², Bonomi, E.² and Siddi, G.²

¹ University “Alma Mater Studiorum”, Bologna, Italy

²CRS4, Pula(CA), Italy

Keywords: RTM, reverse time migration, HPC, Poynting vector, seismic explorations, migration method, exploratory 3D surveys, MPI, parallel computing

Reverse Time Migration (RTM) is not a new imaging technique, it was invented in 1983 by Baisal, Kosloff and Sherwood in order to offer improvements over existing migration methods, especially in cases of steeply dipping structures with strong velocity contrasts. However, it was not until the late 1990s and mainly the 2000s that computational advances allowed the geophysical community to use this technology for exploratory 3D surveys. RTM’s propagation engine, a two-way wave equation, makes this imaging method robust and accurate because it honors the kinematics of the wave phenomena by allowing waves to propagate in all direction regardless velocity model or the direction of propagation. Nevertheless, RTM has its limitations. Two major drawbacks are the artifacts produced by backscattering and the amplitudes of the migrated images, which are not proportional to the subsurface reflectivity.

We built an RTM code starting from an acoustic elastic propagation code, the SimSonic software. SimSonic is freely available 3rd party software suite for the simulation of ultrasound propagation, based on finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) computations of the elastodynamics equations. The SimSonic suite consists of several compiled programs and C source codes, free for use. We used this code as reference. But for the purpose, it was necessary to edit the code to build the whole workflow of the RTM. We implemented an MPI parallelization paradigm to lower the disk occupation and save time.

To reduce the artifacts caused by backscattering we used the Poynting-vector imaging condition. Several attempts to improve the amplitudes are conducted, they are based on illumination compensation with different kinds of stabilization. In order to obtain an high resolution image of the subsurface reflectivity, we implemented the following changes to forward and backward propagator, which are based on SimSonic software: clean trace from direct arrivals, reverse time, add input table of velocity and density, record P-wave signal, time alignment of the signal with the source and apodisation methods.

We established two levels of code parallelization, in order to have results in hours, not in days, and a low consumption of memory: single shot level and multiple shots level. For the first case, we can run simultaneously two synchronized processes to compute the contributions of the imaging condition at each snapshot time, in this fashion we save disk space and time. Since is important to carry out many shots, for the second case, a process must be in charge of summing the image contributions coming from a single shot to generate the final image. The main consequence of this choice was to save time.

To validate the RTM workflow we used as reference, the Marmousi model, a dataset generated by Stanford University.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-06. We acknowledge the CRS4 for the availability of high performance computing resources and support .

References

Edip Baysal, Dan D. Kosloff, and John W. C. Sherwood, Reverse time migration, *Geophysics* 48 (1983), no. 11, 1514–1524

B. Biondi, 3-D Seismic Imaging , *Investigations of Geophysics*, vol. 14, Society of Exploration Geophysicists, 2006

S. Chattopadhyay and G. McMechan, Imaging conditions for prestack reverse time migration, *Geophysics* 73 (2008), no. 3, 81–89

M. Cogan, R. Fletcher, R. King, and D. Nichols, Normalization strategies for reverse-time migration, *SEG Annual meeting Society of Exploration Geophysicists* (2011), 3275–3279

J. Costa, F. Silva, R. Alcántara, J. Schleicher, and A. Novais, Obliquity-correction imaging condition for reverse time migration, *Geophysics* 74 (2009), no. 3, S57–S66

K. Yoon and K. Marfurt, Reverse time migration using the Poynting vector, *Exploration Geophysics* 37 (2006), 102–107

Diaz E., Sava P. (2015) Understanding the reverse time migration backscattering: noise or signal? <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2478.12232>

Parallelising OGSTM – BFM I/O

Coidessa, G., Bolzon, G.

National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: HPC, OGSTM-BFM, I/O parallelisation

This project is part of a restyling work on the OGSTM - BFM model that is used to study the biogeochemical properties of Mediterranean Sea waters. OGS is one of the research centres that are involved in the Copernicus (European Union's Earth observation programme) project, being part of the 6th MFC (Monitoring and Forecasting Centres) which aim is to provide regular and systematic information about the physical state of the ocean and marine ecosystems for the Mediterranean Sea. OGS runs the OGSTM - BFM model (ocean numerical model) assimilating TAC (Thematic Data Assembly Centres) data to generate reanalysis (20 years in the past), analysis (today) and 10-days forecasts of the Mediterranean Sea. This work is aimed at the improvements of the outputs to enhance the dumping capability without affecting the total run time.

The serial Input/Output (I/O) framework (i.e., during I/O operations, variables were dumped by the processor 0 of the first node that collected and dumped all variables from all the processors) has been improved to a I/O parallel distribution framework.

The new parallel I/O distribution features a defined number of writing processors per each node (i.e., the number, from 1 to 6, is specified in the namelist.init namelist) that handle the I/O of the variables to be dumped. Each I/O routine was divided in two parts: in the first block of code `mpi_gatherv` call collects its own variable to dump within each writing rank and then then the variable was dumped. This is applied to each of the nodes of the computation domain taking advantage that the file system permits to dump simultaneously from each node. For the specific case of 1 year reanalysis run (20 computation nodes), dumping time was reduced by an order of ten, while communication time was nearly halved with respect to the serial I/O version (Figure 1). Instead of dumping in parallel a netcdf file, we decided to distribute the parallel dumping through nodes to exploit the bandwidth at it best possibility.

Fig.1 - Timing of New I/O features with 1 procs per Node (#20) for a simulation of 1 year (daily I/O operations).

The proposed solutions to OGSTM model allowed to run the reanalysis with a significant improvements of the computational time cost saving 1330 computational hours per year simulation with 20 nodes and 720 processors (36 procs per node): I/O times passed from 3 hours to half an hour.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-07. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IsraC “HYPER”).

Electromagnetic inversion under the Low Induction Number approximation

Denich, E.¹, Novati, P.¹, and Picotti, S.²

¹University of Trieste, Trieste, Italy

²National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: Low Induction Number, numerical optimization

The aim of electromagnetic (EM) soundings methods in geophysics is to obtain information about the conductivity structure of the earth by recorded measurements taken at the surface. One technique consists of placing a magnetic dipole above the surface. In this case, the electromagnetic induction effect, encoded in Maxwell's equations, produce eddy alternating currents in the soil which on their turn, induce response electromagnetic fields, that can be used to determine the conductivity profile of the ground. The most common dipole configurations consists in a horizontal transmitter loop (vertical dipole) and a receiver loop that can be horizontal (HCP configuration) and vertical (PRP configuration); other two common configurations consist in vertical coplanar loops (VCP configuration) and in vertical coaxial loops (VCX configuration).

We consider a specific application, related to the internal composition of river levees. They may collapse due to the condition of the soils that form the embankment, since water seepage throughout the embankment could generate internal erosion.

To reconstruct geophysical structures from EM measurements, an inversion procedure is needed. One typically defines a forward model for the EM response and then minimize the mismatch between the measured data and the predicted data. The forward model used in the inversion usually consists of a set of locally horizontal homogeneous layers, and a frequently used analytical model is the Low Induction Number (LIN) introduced by McNeill (1980), based on the work of Wait (1962). The induction number is defined as the source-receiver distance divided by the skin depth, which in turns quantifies the effective penetration of the signal. When operating at LIN, the eddy currents of each layer do not interact, and the secondary field measured at the receiver can be approximated as the sum of the independent fields from each individual current loop. A huge advantage of the McNeill reduction is the linearity in the conductivity and the simplicity of the equations. These features make it an excellent model for the design of an inversion procedure to reconstruct the conductivity distribution of the subsurface. An alternative approach is to determine the exact solution in case of a layered earth. Ward and Hohmann (1988) derived integral general solutions for vertical and horizontal magnetic dipole, which can be computed by numerical integration. For the evaluation of the integral equations we consider the semi-analytical numerical approach of Singh and Mogi (2010). In this work we implement four realistic 3-layered earth models and perform an inversion procedure in which we take, as measured data, the results of Singh and Mogi (2010) numerical algorithm and, as forward model, the solutions under the LIN approximation. To solve the minimization problem, defined by the inversion procedure, we use the MATLAB built-in routine *fminunc.m* of the Global Optimization Toolbox (<https://it.mathworks.com/help/optim/ug/fminunc.html>). The algorithm implements an iterative quasi-Newton method based on the BFGS update for the Hessian.

The earth models are used to simulate EM measurements for different thicknesses of the layers. Then we invert these observations to reconstruct the real underground composition. First, we perform the inversion only for HCP configuration, then only for PRP configuration and finally for both configurations coupled (DUALEM acquisition system). The offsets are 2, 4, 6 and 8 m for HCP and 2.1, 4.1, 6.1 and 8.1 m for PRP.

Our analysis shows that in resistive environment the LIN assumption is valid up to offset of 8 m, while in the conductive case the evaluation of the EM field components leads to relative percentage errors greater than 30%, even with offset less than 4 m. These errors have a great impact on the inversion procedure. The PRP array is the one that produces the best results, with errors less than 25%, while the HCP array often provides considerable errors, especially for small thicknesses. Moreover, the combination of the two configurations (DUALEM system) is affected by HCP errors.

To overcome the limitations of the LIN approximation, a possible solution is the implementation of an inversion procedure based on the numerical modelling of the EM fields components.

Fig.1 – Transmitter and receiver coils (left) configurations and an example of layered geological model (right).

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-04.

This research has been funded by the DILEMMA project, “Imaging, modelling, monitoring and design of earthen levees”; Ministero dell’Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare (MATTM), under the framework “Progetti di ricerca finalizzati alla previsione e alla prevenzione dei rischi geologici” (D.D. 524 del 29 novembre 2017).

References

- McNeill, J.D. (1980), Electromagnetic terrain conductivity measurements at low induction numbers, Tech. Note TN-6. Geonics Ltd., Mississauga, ON.
- Singh, N.P. and Mogi, T. (2010), EMDPLER: A F77 program for modelling the EM response of dipolar sources over the non-magnetic layer earth models, *Computer & Geosciences*, 36, 430-440.
- Wait, J.R. (1962), A note on the electromagnetic response of a stratified Earth, *Geophysics*, 27,382-385.
- Ward, S.H. and Hohmann, G.W. (1988) Electromagnetic theory for geophysical applications. In: Nabighian, M.N., (ed.), *Electromagnetic Methods in Applied Geophysics, Theory vol. 1*. Society of Exploration Geophysicists, Tulsa, Oklahoma, pp. 131-311.

Role of Ocean Mesoscale variability on low-level atmospheric dynamics, cloud cover and Rainfall

Desbiolles, F.^{1,2} and Pasquero, C.^{1,3}

¹Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of Milano Bicocca, Italy

²National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Trieste, Italy

³Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC), Turin, Italy

Keywords: mesoscale air-sea interactions, clouds, rainfall

One of the larger challenges facing the climate modelling community is that climate models appear to poorly represent some of the key regional circulation processes and as a result, struggle to produce reasonable simulations of regional rainfall patterns. The difficulty is partly due to the regional climate dynamics being complex and strongly modulated by processes operating on the global scale down to regional and local scales. Notably, air-sea interactions, which play a paramount role for both fluid dynamics over a wide spectrum of variability, influence the thermodynamical balance and the exchange of key properties at the interface. The local heat and momentum fluxes are then shaping the vertical structure of the atmosphere and the ocean, basin-scale circulation, climate and therefore water cycle. We focus here on the sensitivity of local and regional atmospheric dynamics to the so-called ocean thermal feedbacks.

Two main mechanisms have been proposed to describe the Marine Atmospheric Boundary Layer (MABL) response to small-scale spatial and temporal variability of Sea Surface Temperature (SST). The so-called Downward Momentum (DM) flux mixing mechanism and the Pressure Adjustment (PA) mechanism. The DM mechanism brings into play the turbulence and large eddies with the MABL stimulated by the turbulent fluctuations of momentum, temperature and moisture; their-self driven by SST gradient. The PA mechanism, initially proposed in a context of tropical dynamics, causes wind divergence in the MABL due to surface atmospheric pressure forced by temperature patterns. It ensues a linear relationship between wind divergence and Laplacian of SST. The above two mechanisms operate from meso- to submesoscales but it remains unclear the favourable conditions which makes one process prevailing on the other-one (Pasquero et al.,2020).

Over the Mediterranean, we first show that the Downward Momentum (DM) mixing mechanism is prevailing at daily timescale notably due to the stable nature of the air-column over the Mediterranean. Autumn season is the period during which the DM mechanism is more determining for the surface wind speed. We then show the corresponding vertical structure of the MABL over Sea Surface Temperature patterns, with a significant imprint until 925 hPa. Finally, we show that the downwind SST gradient modifies significantly cloud cover, reducing when the lows corresponds to warm-to-cold SST patterns, increasing for a cold-to-warm scenario. Rainfall events are significantly more (less) frequent over extreme negative (positive) Downwind SST gradients (Desbiolles et al., in rev.). More specifically, the 25% strongest warm-to-cold fronts are associated with a mean increase of cloud cover of $10\pm 5\%$ ($25\pm 12\%$) and a mean increase in the probability of a rain event of $15\pm 6\%$ ($22\pm 10\%$), with respect to the average values for the entire period (Fall only). The 25% strongest cold-to-warm fronts are associated with a mean decrease of cloud cover of $4\pm 2\%$ ($14\pm 8\%$) and a mean decrease in the probability of a rain event of $10\pm 4\%$ ($18\pm 8\%$) for the entire Period (Fall only).

Over Southern Africa, SST gradients, notably over the great Agulhas system system, influence the vertical air column up to the troposphere, and mesoscale ocean patterns significantly modify incoming landward moisture fluxes (Desbiolles et al., 2018). Furthermore, the seasonal effect of air-sea interactions on the low-level atmosphere tends to strengthen the Angola-Low pressure system during austral summer. Specifically, the Angola-Benguela Frontal Zone (ABFZ), convergence area of the cold Northern Benguela current and the warm tropical Atlantic, contains spatial structures corresponding to the first Rossby radius of deformation which promote atmospheric near-surface

baroclinicity and modify in turn the regional circulation. The Low-pressure system, associated with the confluence zone of low-level moisture fluxes originating from tropical and sub-tropical western Indian and tropical Atlantic Oceans, is then modified and, consequently, it generates a modulation of moisture distribution in the region on daily to seasonal timescales (Desbiolles et al.,2020).

To conclude, the thermal oceanic feedbacks act locally and rapidly by modifying the air-column stability. A cold-to-warm (warm-to-cold) flow favors wind convergence (divergence), promote upward (downward) motion, increasing (decreasing) cloud cover and associated rainfall. These processes also act remotely and have important upscaling effects at seasonal and regional scales. We have seen, as an example, substantial changes in austral summer rainfall over the continent and moisture flux entering southern Africa. These results indicate the importance of taking into account the mesoscale variability of the ocean for accurate atmospheric simulations.

Acknowledgements

Support for this study has been provided by HPC-TRES grant number 2020-10 and ESA contract n. 4000127657/19/NL/FF/gp. We acknowledge the CINECA computing facilities and the help provided to use the resources.

References

Desbiolles, F., Blamey, R.C., Illig, S., James, R., Barimalala, R., Renault, L. and Reason, C.J.C. (2018) Upscaling impact of wind/sea surface temperature mesoscale interactions on southern Africa austral summer climate. *Int. J. of Clim.* 38,4651–4660.

Desbiolles, F., Howard, E., Blamey, R.C., Barimalala, R., Hart, N.C.G. and Reason, C.J.C. (2020) Role of ocean mesoscale structures in shaping the Angola-Low pressure system and the southern Africa rainfall. *Clim. Dyn.*,1-20.

Desbiolles, F., Alberti, M., and Meroni, A.M., Hamouda, M.E.A. and Pasquero, C. (in rev.) Links between sea surface temperature structures, clouds and rainfall: Study case of the Mediterranean Sea. *Geophys. Res. Let.*

Pasquero, C., Desbiolles, F. and Meroni, A.N. (2020) Air-sea interactions in the cold wakes of tropical cyclones. *Geophys. Res. Let.*, e2020GL091185.

Extreme event waves in marine ecosystems

Di Biagio, V., Cossarini, G., Salon, S. and Solidoro, C.

National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: extreme events, marine ecosystems, numerical modeling, Mediterranean Sea

Extreme events affecting the Earth system have been widely investigated in hydrology, atmospheric science and oceanography. However, extreme events occurring in the marine biosphere have received relatively little attention and their spatial extension, if considered, was typically evaluated in retrospect.

We have recently proposed a novel method to characterise and classify extreme events in marine ecosystems on the basin scale, by considering extreme events connected in space and time as a sort of a “wave”, which we defined as “extreme event wave” (EEW; Di Biagio et al. 2020).

We identified local extreme events as peaks over the 99th percentile threshold computed on the time series of the variable under study (Fig. 1, left panel). Then, we defined EEWs as sets of local extreme events that are connected in space and time. Finally, we introduced some indexes both to describe the spatio-temporal features of the EEWs and to evaluate their impact on the marine ecosystem. In particular, we quantified the persistence of an EEW on a certain area by the uniformity index, its overall intensity by the mean severity index and its exceptionality for the considered area by the anomaly index.

We chose the surface chlorophyll concentration as a first example of application of the method. Chlorophyll is in fact one of the essential ocean variables and it is representative of the marine ecosystem state and evolution. Moreover, since high frequency and seamless data in time and space are mandatory to properly detect extreme events on the basin scale, we used chlorophyll data provided by a coupled hydrodynamic-biogeochemical model. Daily data of surface chlorophyll were taken from a simulation of the Mediterranean Sea ecosystem in the 1994-2012 period (Di Biagio et al. 2019) and produced by the MITgcm-BFM model at 1/12° horizontal resolution. Due to both the high number (>50) of state variables included in the model and the 150s adopted timestep, the simulation consumed 150000 core-hours on GALILEO and PICO clusters at CINECA and generated 8 terabyte of output data.

We characterised all the EEWs identified in the model simulation by computing the indexes of spatio-temporal localisation and impact on the marine ecosystem. Then, we reconstructed a bio-regionalisation of the Mediterranean Sea associated to the main EEW regimes, as dominant combinations of these indexes. In particular, we conducted a fuzzy clustering analysis (Bezdek et al. 1984) on the mean annual maps of duration, uniformity, mean severity and anomaly and we adopted a fuzziness parameter equal to 2. We identified seven Mediterranean Sea regions from maximum membership values (Fig.1, right panel) and we evaluated the robustness of the clusterisation by computing the “confusion index” (Burrough et al., 1997). Finally, we conducted a trend analysis and we found that there are not significant trends (i.e. annual variations higher than 1 %) in the mean severity of chlorophyll EEWs within the seven clusters, whereas some trends were found for other indexes.

The reliability of the proposed method was supported by the comparison of the results with the available data and previous studies. Therefore, this method can be applied also to other ecosystem variables, provided that sensitivity analyses on the local threshold are performed, in order to select suitable values to highlight the typology of extreme events for the specific variable under investigation.

Fig.1 – Left panel: conceptual diagram of covered area (A) and duration (T) spatio-temporal indexes of an extreme event wave (EEW, green shape), as a region where the peaks over 99th threshold records (POTs, top right box) of the ecosystem variable are connected in time and space. Right panel: Mediterranean Sea bio-regionalisation obtained from duration, mean severity, uniformity and anomaly index values of surface chlorophyll EEWs in 1994-2012, with black points indicating a high (>0.7) confusion index. Please refer to Di Biagio et al. 2020 for further details.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2016-04. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IsraC (IsraC “IsC34_BIOMEDCO”, “IsC41_BIOMEDXT”, “IsC45_BLOMEDXT”).

References

- Di Biagio, V., Cossarini, G., Salon, S. and Solidoro, C. (2020) Extreme event waves in marine ecosystems: an application to Mediterranean Sea surface chlorophyll. *Biogeosciences* 17, 5967-5988, <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-17-5967-2020>.
- Di Biagio, V., Cossarini, G., Salon, S., Lazzari, P., Querin, S., Sannino, G. and Solidoro C. (2019) Temporal scales of variability in the Mediterranean Sea ecosystem: Insight from a coupled model, *J. Mar. Syst.*, 197, 103176, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2019.05.002>.
- Bezdek, J. C., Ehrlich, R. and Full, W. (1984) FCM: The fuzzy c-means clustering algorithm, *Comput. Geosci.*, 10, 191–203, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0098-3004\(84\)90020-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0098-3004(84)90020-7).
- Burrough, P. A., van Gaans, P. F. M. and Hootsmans, R. (1997) Continuous classification in soil survey: spatial correlation, confusion and boundaries, *Geoderma*, 77, 115–135, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0016-7061\(97\)00018-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0016-7061(97)00018-9)

Climate change impact on flood hazards over Italy

García-Valdecasas Ojeda, M.^{1,2}, Coppola, E.², Fantini, A.², Di Sante, F.², Raffaele, F.², Nogherotto, R.², Giorgi, F.²

¹National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, Trieste, Italy

²Earth System Physics Section, International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), Trieste, Italy

Keywords: flood hazard assessment, CHyM model, RegCM model, Italy

Floods are one of the most devastating natural hazards with significant impacts on humans and ecosystems. This kind of extreme event is expected that increase in frequency and severity because of climate change. Therefore, flood forecasting and risk estimation are essential tools for protecting the population from flood-related damages.

This work aims to assess flood hazards over Italy, in both present and future conditions. To do this, a model chain approach based on climate and hydrological models was applied. Thus, the CETEMPS Hydrological Model (CHyM) was used to complete a set of hydrological simulations for nine separate domains covering the entire Italian territory, obtaining thus river discharge at an hourly temporal scale. As the first step, we obtained hydrological data for present conditions. Climate data were obtained by using the ICTP RegCM Regional Climate model driven by two different datasets: (1) the reanalysis data from ERA-Interim, and (2) the outputs from a global climate model, the HadGEM2-ES. These high-resolution climate data along with observations from the GRidded Italian Precipitation Hourly Observations (GRIPHO), also at high resolution, were subsequently used to feed CHyM. Once simulated present conditions, river discharge projections for the future were obtained. To do this, hydrological simulations were completed using now projections from the RegCM driven by HadGEM2-ES, for two future periods, a near (2020- 2049) and a far (2070-2099) future. Changes in discharge were analyzed through the delta changes of different metrics related to the historical period (1976-2005), and flood estimations were computed through changes in frequency and severity of extreme discharges.

The results showed that hydrological simulations present a general quite good agreement with observations. Concerning projections, an increase in frequency and severity of flood events is expected by the end of the century in Italy, indicating a significant flood hazard in this region. This study could serve as a starting point for estimating flood hazards using model chain approaches.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-02.

Portable climate data analytics at scale through software containers

Giannotta, A.¹, Elia, D.^{1,2}, Fiore, S.³, Palazzo, C.¹, D'Anca, A.¹, Aloisio, G.^{1,2}

¹Advanced Scientific Computing Division, Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui cambiamenti climatici (CMCC), Lecce, Italy

²Department of Engineering for Innovation, University of Salento

³Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science, University of Trento

Keywords: climate, software containers, high performance computing, big data analytics

Ophidia is a big data analytics framework able to manage huge workflows in a really efficient and effective manner. It performs in-memory computations on multiple nodes in a parallel and workflow-based fashion, by using operators that are optimized for climate data.

The software is mainly composed of:

- a Server that manages the operations of all other Ophidia components
- one or more I/O & Analytics Servers, processing data cube fragments in-memory
- an Analytics Framework that processes and manages data cubes, by providing a common way to run distributive tasks (operators) on large set of fragments
- and a client-side terminal to interact with the entire data analytics framework

The deployment of a software that allows climate data management on large datasets must be scalable, but also easy to use for end-users that work on different systems. To deal with this problem, it is fundamental to exploit the power, portability and simplicity of containers, which is a novel concept in HPC environments.

Lightweight software virtualization, in particular OS-level virtualization, brings containers to life, by overcoming the guest OS existence (thanks to OS kernel sharing) and creating an isolated software environment packaged into a so-called container image: just a simple, portable and consistent file that contains applications plus all their dependencies and libraries bundled with other binaries and configuration files needed to run your software. Docker is the most popular container engine and the aforementioned text file, called Dockerfile, can be exploited by using the container engine interface to build the container image and then an instance of that (namely a container) can be run on your host system. However, this approach is not suitable for HPC systems, especially for performance and security reasons (e.g., the Docker daemon requires root access). Hence, after an appropriate Dockerfile preparation, we can use another, more HPC-oriented container technology called Singularity (provided by Sylabs) to build the container image and run it everywhere, while complying with HPC security policies at data center level and performance requirements.

A preliminary containerized version of the Ophidia framework components has been created with the goal of targeting different infrastructures (i.e, with Docker and Singularity). This activity went through several challenges, such as: (i) dynamic users/group mapping in container building and running phases, (ii) the use of host optimized libraries, (iii) the generalization of Ophidia components set up when working with different container engines and target systems, (iv) network issues between components in this multi-container deploy, (v) the interaction with different resource managers.

In this preliminary implementation, the Ophidia components are mapped onto different containers, communicating with each other (as shown in Fig.1).

A lightweight python program is also under development, aiming to manage the deployment/undeployment of containerized Ophidia components with Docker and Singularity on different infrastructures.

Fig.1 - High-level view of the logical connections of the Ophidia containerized components (including the host's resource manager).

Finally, a set of strong scalability tests have been run to compare the performance of the containerized version of Ophidia (Singularity-based) with the classic deployment (the bare-metal version) on a single node of the Zeus supercomputer at CMCC. The measured parallel execution time proves that, compared to bare-metal deployment, software containerization is well-suited for running in the HPC environment and the introduced overhead is negligible at all examined scales.

The results of this activity, although preliminary, already show the effectiveness of the containerization approach in terms of improved deployability and portability of a data analytics software, such as the Ophidia framework, across a range of different HPC/Cloud infrastructures.

Future work will include the full containerization of all Ophidia components, the benchmarking of the full containerized stack on large-scale supercomputers, as well as a stronger integration with the HPC software ecosystem and the evaluation of additional containerization technologies.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-05.

References

D. Elia, S. Fiore, A. D'Anca, C. Palazzo, I. Foster, D. N. Williams, G. Aloisio, "An in-memory based framework for scientific data analytics". In Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers (CF '16), May 16-19, 2016, Como, Italy, pp. 424-429

S. Fiore, A. D'Anca, C. Palazzo, I. T. Foster, D. N. Williams, G. Aloisio, "Ophidia: Toward Big Data Analytics for eScience", ICCS 2013, June 5-7, 2013 Barcelona, Spain, ICCS, volume 18 of Procedia Computer Science, page 2376-2385. Elsevier, 2013

David Brayford and Sofia Vallecorsa. 2020. "Deploying Scientific AI Networks at Petaflop Scale on Secure Large Scale HPC Production Systems with Containers". PASC '20. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 6, 1-8.

European Extreme Precipitation: the effects of spatio-temporal resolution of the data

Hamouda M.¹, Pasquero C.^{1,2}

¹University of Milano Bicocca, Milan, Italy.

²Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC), Turin, Italy

Keywords: Extreme Precipitation, WRF, high resolution.

European wintertime precipitation is known to be skilfully estimated in reanalysis data and model simulations since it is highly correlated with large scale, low frequency modes of variability, namely the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO). Since the NAO is mainly a wintertime mode of variability, the skill of estimating precipitation becomes more limited in the other seasons, most importantly in the summer, in which precipitation is mainly a result of mesoscale convection. In this study, we use the Weather Research and Forecast (WRF) model, to show the added value of using a high resolution, convection-permitting model to estimate precipitation extremes. The results show that WRF succeeds to correct the failure of ERA-Interim reanalysis to capture the positive trends of European extreme precipitation in summer and transition seasons that are indicated by the observational data (EOBS) and previous literature. While in winter, negative extreme precipitation trends dominate the European domain due to more frequent positive NAO phase during the past decades.

Figure: Ratio of Positive-to-Negative extreme precipitation frequency trend for different datasets, showing the failure of ERA reanalysis to capture the correct trends in summer and transition seasons. Ratio>1 means more positive trends than negative.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2017-03. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IsraC “HYPER”).

Machine Learning for Climate Change applications

Immorlano, F.^{1,3}, Accarino G.^{2,3}, Chiarelli M.^{2,3}, Aloisio G.^{1,3}

¹ Department of Innovation Engineering, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

² Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences and Technologies, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

³ Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) Foundation, Lecce, Italy

Keywords: machine learning, deep learning, climate change, climate science

Climate Change has already had undeniable effects that people are facing, and scientists have high confidence that they will get worse over time. All the traditional techniques currently used in the biggest meteorological centers for Climate Science applications are extremely intensive from a computational standpoint and very time-consuming, requiring — for each simulation — at least a parallel implementation to be ran on hundreds of thousands of Central Processing Units (CPUs) for weeks or even months. Moreover, traditional models are highly sensitive to initial conditions that have to be accurate in order to mitigate approximation errors. Instead, concerning Deep Learning (DL) and, more generally, Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, a small number of Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) are sufficient for their execution and, after the training phase, few minutes or fractions of a minute are needed to make a prediction. Moreover, they are basically data-driven approaches, meaning that they learn complex and non-linear spatio-temporal relationships directly from data (Mudigonda et al., 2017), without needing the physical equation governing the phenomenon of interest to be specified, in this way avoiding also the approximation errors if the equation is not known very well.

One of the most imminent Climate Change threats is represented by the intensification of the frequency, intensity and duration of the extreme weather events, including Tropical Cyclones (TCs). The latter are large-scale cyclones with a warm core, and they originate over tropical or subtropical waters with an organized deep convection (Roy and Kovordányi, 2012) and a closed surface wind circulation. There are seven cyclone formation basins in the world, and roughly 80 TCs develop globally each year. The wind speed of a TC can exceed 33 ms^{-1} , and the typical lifetime is 3–5 days, but it can become 2–3 weeks if the cyclone remains over sea (Emanuel, 2003).

Two of the main tasks concerning TCs are Detection and Tracking. They are closely interrelated, indeed the former is the identification of the position of the cyclonic phenomenon on a climatic map in a specific past time, exploiting values of meaningful physical variables (e.g., Sea Surface Temperature, Pressure, Wind velocity, Vorticity, etc.). The latter is performed in a subsequent phase because, starting from the positions found through the detection, it consists in the reconstruction of the trajectory the cyclone followed over several past time instants at steps of 6, 12 or 24 h. Both tasks are performed by means of tracking schemes based on subjective thresholds and applied on numerical simulation outcomes or reanalysis data. This implies the presence of biases related to the knowledge of the phenomenon by the author, the lack of coherence between the schemes used by different meteorological centers (Horn et al., 2014) and the basin-dependence because the physical processes that characterize each basin are different from those of the other basins, requiring basin-specific thresholds to be used. ML can help to tackle these issues.

Besides detection and tracking tasks, TCs Forecasting involves the prediction of several interrelated features, such as the frequency, the cyclone's track, its intensity, etc. One of the goals of the present Ph.D. research project is the TC track forecasting, which consists of predicting the TC's movement over the next several days every 6, 12 or 24 h. Moreover, the use of generative models, like Generative Adversarial Networks, would give the chance to perform the Cloud Motion Reconstruction task, this way making the model able also to generate the image representing the structure and the shape that the surrounding clouds will assume in a subsequent time instant.

The research will involve also other Climate Science case studies, like the interesting problem of Downscaling that is the process of increasing the spatial resolution of climatic fields, starting from

their coarser resolution and which is motivated by the coarse-grained Global Climate Models that produce low resolution maps without the ability to resolve local and regional physical processes which are critical to understand the climatic system (Vandal et al., 2019). Even in this case, the workload of traditional dynamical and statistical downscaling techniques is computationally heavy and ML models represent a promising solution.

The present Ph.D. research will begin with an extensive study of the TCs phenomenology, of the current operational tracking schemes and ML and DL algorithms with a specific focus on those already employed in Climate Science applications and in TCs forecasting. Then, an adequate dataset comprehensive of satellite images and related metadata will be constructed and a Deep Neural Network architecture will be designed, implemented and tested for the TCs Track Forecasting and Cloud Motion Reconstruction tasks. Subsequently, other ML algorithms will be examined to forecast other TCs features, and the chance to implement a ML model for the detection and tracking tasks and to develop an informative dashboard available for the scientific community will be evaluated too. Of course, the research will also include the extension of the application of ML and DL algorithms to other Climate Change use cases, like the Downscaling one.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-04. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IscraC “HYPER”).

References

Emanuel, K. (2003) Tropical cyclones. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences* 31. 75-104. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.earth.31.100901.141259>

Vandal, T., Kodra, E., Ganguly, A. (2019) Intercomparison of machine learning methods for statistical downscaling: the case of daily and extreme precipitation. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology* 137, 557-570. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-018-2613-3>

Horn, M., Walsh, K., Zhao, M., Camargo, S.J., Scoccimarro, E., Murakami, H., Wang, H., Ballinger, A., Kumar, A., Shaevitz, D.A., Jonas, J.A., Oouchi, K. (2014) Tracking scheme dependence of simulated tropical cyclone response to idealized climate simulations. *Journal of Climate* 27, 9197-9213. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-14-00200.1>

Mudigonda, M., Kim, S., Mahesh, A., Ebrahimi Kahou, S., Kashinath, K., Williams, D., Michalski, V., O'Brien, T., Prabhat, M. (2017) Segmenting and tracking extreme climate events using neural networks. *Deep Learning for Physical Sciences (DLPS) Workshop*

Roy, C. and Kovordányi, R. (2012) Tropical cyclone track forecasting techniques — A review. *Atmospheric Research* 104-105, 40-69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2011.09.012>

HPC implementations in the SHYFEM hydrodynamic model using the PETSc library and application to modern architectures

Laurent, C.¹, Bnà, S.², Pascolo, E.², Sartori, A.³ and Umgiesser, G.⁴

¹National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics – OGS, Italy

²CINECA, Italy

³International School for Advanced Studies – SISSA, Italy

³Institute of Marine Science – ISMAR/CNR, Italy

Keywords: fluid dynamics, oceanography, solver, finite elements, PETSc, SHYFEM

Research activities in environmental fluid dynamics require an increasing need for accuracy and computing productivity, solving problems becoming always bigger and obtaining faster solutions. The modern source codes must be re-designed to follow the changing technology and increase their performance to reduce computational cost. In this context, the SHYFEM Shallow water HYdrodynamic Finite Element Model was recently parallelised using domain decomposition based on the Message Passing Interface (MPI) communication protocol. The Portable, Extensible Toolkit for Scientific Computation Toolkit for Advanced Optimization - PETSc library was chosen to replace the previous sequential solver of SHYFEM.

The details of the developments done to insert PETSc into the source code of SHYFEM are presented, together with profilings and benchmark analysis of the software before and after the implementations. The implementations made during the GPU Hackathon of Helmholtz (september 2020) are as well presented; they allow to use the nVIDIA AmgX solver on the GPU employing PETSc as a frontend through the AmgXWrapper. Aside from the optimization of the calls to the PETSc solver, some performance issues are identified and solutions are suggested. Finally, a modern compilation setup based on the Meson build system is provided as an alternative to the original Makefiles and configures a set of integration tests on both the CPU and GPU. All the developments were tested, profiled and benchmarked on the CPUs and GPUs of the Galileo and Marconi 100 clusters of CINECA.

On the Marconi 100 cluster of the CINECA, in the original state of the parallel SHYFEM program running a one year long simulation with 12 MPI processes and a problem size of 18,000 unknowns per process would have required more than 28 hours of computation. With the PETSc library and the new implementations it is now running in less than 3 hours.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was performed in the context of the Master in High Performance Computing - MHPC co-founded by SISSA and ICTP, and were supported by OGS and CINECA under the HPC-TRES program award number 2020-06. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (Iskra “OGS20_PRACE_P”).

References

PETSc Portable, Extensible Toolkit for Scientific Computation Toolkit for Advanced Optimization : <https://www.mcs.anl.gov/petsc/>

SHYFEM, Finite Element Model for Coastal Seas, User Manual : <https://github.com/shyfem-cm/shyfem/blob/develop/femdoc/final/shyfem.pdf>

MPI : the Message Passing Interface library <http://www.mpi-forum.org>

AmgX solver : Multi-Grid Accelerated Linear Solvers for Industrial Applications, <https://github.com/NVIDIA/AMGX>

AmgXWrapper: An interface between PETSc and the NVIDIA AmgX library, P-Y Chuang and L. A. Barba, 2017, Journal of Open Source Software 2(16) DOI: 10.21105/joss.00280 <https://github.com/barbagroup/AmgXWrapper>

The Meson build system <https://mesonbuild.com/>

The Galileo supercomputer - CINECA <https://www.hpc.cineca.it/hardware/galileo>

The Marconi 100 accelerated system – CINECA <https://www.hpc.cineca.it/hardware/marconi100>

Scientific visualisation and machine learning (experiences from HPC-TRES)

Miró, A.

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), Barcelona, Spain

Keywords: data, visualization, tools, 3D, ParaView, experience, machine learning

Most people have an idea of the ocean as a surface; however, the third dimension is extremely important. Sunlight penetration or vertical transport processes are key to biological dynamics. The OGSTM-BFM, i.e., OGS Tracer Model – Biogeochemical Flux Model (Vichi et al., 2015) code uses highly optimized 3D transport reactions non-linear PDE to model biogeochemical processes on the Mediterranean Sea. Therefore, efficient data analysis and visualization is crucial to comprehend the dynamics of the sea, for example, to understand the spatial variability of relevant magnitudes such as chlorophyll (Lazzari, 2012) and phosphate (Lazzari, 2016) concentration.

Open-source visualization platforms such as Blender (see Fig. 1) or ParaView (Ahrens, 2005) provide powerful data analysis and visualization tools. In particular, ParaView is built on top of the VTK library (Schroeder, 2000) and has been designed to analyze extremely large datasets using distributed memory computing resources, ideally to be run on supercomputers. Data exploration can be performed either interactively in 3D or programmatically using its python interface. Moreover, it can be easily extended by means of plug-ins written in either Python or C++. The present work shows the consolidation of the *OGS ParaView Suite*, a set of filters and plug-ins that extend ParaView capabilities to enable the visualization of biogeochemical model outputs for marine environments Sea from OGSTM-BFM and/or Copernicus Marine services such as the Mediterranean. These set of tools are openly available on Github.

The workflow for bringing biogeochemical data from OGSTM-BFM to ParaView is the following: firstly, the *OGS2Paraview* script is used to generate mesh and master files. These files are used by ParaView to relate the variables and the timesteps and to generate the rectilinear grid. Then, the reader plugin allows to seamlessly open the dataset on ParaView. Once in the application, a number of tools have been developed to work with various masks, for example, to select sub-basins, coast and open-sea or to cut the mesh. Other tools have been developed are, for example, the computation of gradients, spatial and temporal statistics, climatologies, comparison and aggregation of variables among others. This data can be visualized in three dimensions and exported back to NetCDF or Python Numpy format. The suite has various two-dimensional plotting tools such as high-resolution surface maps, depth profiles, spaghetti and Hovmoeller plots. Another of ParaView's capabilities is to be able to work in a client/server configuration, allowing to have the data in a powerful machine (server) and using the local machine (client) just for visualization. The client/server configuration is advantageous as the data (usually in the range of terabytes of information) does not need to be transferred to the local machine. Moreover, in some circumstances, the rendering is also done in the server, thus enabling the use of accelerators such as GPUs.

This work has enabled the author to gain experience in the field of data analysis and visualization. Quoting F. Nietzsche: “one repays a teacher poorly if one always remains only a student”, the author wishes that this knowledge can be passed over to the group and the suite can be thoroughly used for further analyses. The author also wishes to highlight the importance of multidisciplinary research, coming from a different background (Computational Fluid Dynamics, CFD). He is now a researcher at Barcelona Supercomputing Center working in data analysis of CFD data using machine learning. Finally, the author would like to wish a lot of success and good fortune to his former colleagues and friends. May we see each other again!

Fig.1 – Render of a chlorophyll map over the Mediterranean Sea using Blender.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2018-02. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IscraC “HYPER”).

References

- Vichi M., Lo Vichi M., Lovato T., Lazzari P., Cossarini G., Gutierrez Mlot E., Mattia G., Masina S., McKiver W. J., Pinardi N., Solidoro C., Tedesco L., Zavatarelli M. (2015). The Biogeochemical Flux Model (BFM): Equation Description and User Manual. *BFM version 5.1*. BFM Report series N. 1, Release 1.1, July 2015, Bologna, Italy, <http://bfm-community.eu>, pp. 104
- Lazzari, P., Solidoro, C., Salon, S., and Bolzon, G. (2016). Spatial variability of phosphate and nitrate in the Mediterranean Sea: A modeling approach. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 108: 39–52.
- Lazzari, P., Solidoro, C., Ibello, V., Salon, S., Teruzzi, A., Béranger, K., Colella, S., Crise, A., (2012). Sea-sonal and inter-annual variability of plankton chloro-phyll and primary production in the Mediterranean Sea: a modelling approach. *Biogeosciences*, 9:217–233.
- Ahrens, J., Geveci, B., Law, C. (2005). Paraview: An end-user tool for large data visualization. *The visualization handbook*, 717.
- Schroeder, W. J., Avila, L. S., Hoffman, W. (2000). Visualizing with VTK: a tutorial. *IEEE Computer graphics and applications*, 20(5), 20-27.

High-throughput task management for climate analysis workflows

Musio, M.¹, Elia, D.^{1,2}, Fiore, S.³, D'Anca, A.¹, Aloisio, G.^{1,2}

¹Advanced Scientific Computing Division, Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui cambiamenti climatici (CMCC), Lecce, Italy

²Department of Engineering for Innovation, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

³Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science, University of Trento, Trento, Italy

Keywords: climate workflows, high performance computing, big data analytics, message queue, resource management

In the field of high-performance computing and high-performance data analysis for the Earth system, the management of complex experiments composed of multiple connected tasks has been facilitated by the use of workflows which automate complex calculations and support scientific reproducibility and sharing of results. A workflow can consist of hundreds of thousands of data-oriented analysis operators which perform processing, manipulation and analysis of scientific datasets.

In the eScience landscape, the Ophidia system (CMCC) provides a High-Performance Data Analytics framework for multidimensional scientific data joining HPC paradigms with scientific data analytics approaches. A high-level representation of the Ophidia system includes four fundamental blocks representing (i) the Ophidia server that takes care of managing, scheduling, submitting and monitoring analytics jobs, (ii) the analytics framework nodes that deal with the execution of parallel tasks, named operators, running on compute nodes over multidimensional distributed data, the (iii) I/O & analytics nodes that are instead devoted to the I/O operations on the underlying storage system and, finally, (iv) the storage system.

In the latest Ophidia release (v1.5.x), job requests are submitted through an HPC resource manager that takes care of allocating the resources needed to execute the user's request. Since the HPC resource managers are designed to best manage large applications that are typically launched simultaneously on multiple threads or processes, the scheduling of workflows consisting of a large number of heterogeneous (even very short) tasks is a big challenge for today's HPC scheduling systems.

To overcome some limitations introduced by today's HPC resource managers in the processing of climate workflows, and aiming to increase both scalability and performance, we have developed a new pull job scheduling system based on a message queue system. The message queue is a software component capable of containing messages to facilitate the asynchronous communication between different entities. Various messaging systems have been considered and our choice fell on the RabbitMQ message queue. In our case, the RabbitMQ system has been exploited to manage communication between the Ophidia Server and the Ophidia Framework. In particular, the current preliminary design of the new system involves using a new software component that has been implemented and integrated into the Ophidia system. The new component is currently responsible for the submission and cancellation of operator tasks. The previous push-based job submission approach performed through the HPC resource manager has been replaced with a pull-based one using a multi-threading component that integrates RabbitMQ functionalities. Obviously, this system can also be distributed over multiple nodes, thus more compute nodes that consume messages from the same Job queue can be pre-allocated via the HPC batch scheduler.

Fig.1 - Overview of the new system designed and integrated with the existing Ophidia system.

The new system was integrated with the existing Ophidia system and preliminary tests on the Zeus supercomputer have been performed at the CMCC SuperComputing Centre. The initial tests are quite promising and show the suitability of the proposed scheduling architecture for overcoming the well-known HPC resource manager limitations. Full integration with Ophidia and further tests on the Zeus Supercomputer are planned for the coming months. In addition, a performance comparison targeting real world applications will also be performed, to further validate the approach. Of course, additional extensions will also relate to a closer integration with the key components of the Ophidia framework.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-04.

References

1. S. Jha, J. Qiu, A. Luckow, P. Mantha, G. Fox. “A Tale of Two Data-Intensive Paradigms: Applications, Abstractions, and Architectures”, RADICAL, Rutgers University, Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA Indiana University, USA
2. S. Fiore, A. D’Anca, D. Elia, C. Palazzo, I. Foster, D. Williams, G. Aloisio, “Ophidia: a full software stack for scientific data analytics”
3. S. Fiore, A. D’Anca, D. Elia, C. Palazzo, F. Antonio, I. Foster, G. Aloisio, “Towards High Performance Data Analytics for Climate Change”, Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change Foundation, Lecce, Italy, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy, University of Chicago & Argonne National Laboratory, Chicago, USA
4. “Documentation: Table of Contents.” RabbitMQ, www.rabbitmq.com/documentation.html
5. J. Vineet, L. Xia, “A Survey of Distributed Message Broker Queues”

Mixed precision and SL-DG advection model

Paronuzzi Ticco, S.V.¹, Tintó, O.¹, Acosta, M.¹, Tumolo, G.²

¹BSC Earth Sciences Department, Barcelona, Spain

²European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, Reading, United Kingdom

At the beginning of 2021, a mixed precision version of the NEMO code will be included into the official NEMO repository. The proposed optimization despite being not at all trivial, is not new, and quite popular nowadays. In fact, for historical reasons many computational models over-engineer the numerical precision, which leads to an under-optimal exploitation of computational infrastructures. By solving this miss-adjustment a conspicuous payback in terms of efficiency and throughput can be gained: we are not only taking a step toward a more environmentally friendly science, sometimes we are actually pushing the horizon of experiment feasibility a little further. For being able to smoothly include the changes needed in the official release an automatic workflow has been implemented: we attempt to minimize the number of changes required and, at the same time, maximize the number of variables that can be computed using single precision. Here we present a general sketch of the tool and workflow used and talk about the adaptation we need to implement for using the same tool with a different code: the dwarf SL-DG, developed at ECMWF by Giovanni Tumolo.

A three-dimensional numerical model for the noise propagation in an inhomogeneous medium

Petris, G.

University of Trieste, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: underwater acoustic, FDTD, complex source

The low-frequency noise generated by naval vessels is among the major noise pollution sources in the ocean [1]. The acoustic pressure originated by the propeller's rotation propagates inside the water column. It is continuously scattered by the seafloor and the ocean surface, making difficult the numerical approach to noise propagation.

We adopt the Finite Difference Time Domain method to solve the wave equation. It allows us to consider complex sources propagating in an inhomogeneous domain. The model implemented uses a second-order central difference scheme and a Perfectly Matched Layer [2] to damp the spurious reflection at the open boundary.

Most of the underwater acoustic studies [3, 4] rely on the simple spherically symmetric monopole source. However, more complex sources, like dipole and quadrupole (Fig.1), are characterized by a specific directivity, which may significantly affect the resulting acoustic field.

In particular, we study propagation of monopole, dipole, and quadrupole-like sources in a Pekeris waveguide, which is considered archetypal of a marine environment. The results show how dipole and quadrupole are less efficient in propagating energy far from the source and how the directivity modifies the measured sound pressure level on the waveguide. The reflection of the acoustic energy at the seabed is strongly affected by the source's rotation, which is only evident for the dipole and quadrupole sources. Moreover, the dipole axis rotation enhances or diminishes the ability to transfer energy inside the acoustic waveguide.

The dimension of the problem renders necessary the use of the HPC infrastructure. The code uses an efficient OpenMP implementation to speed-up the computational time.

Fig.1 - Sound Pressure Level of a quadrupole source along the x-z plane passing through the source in a homogenous water column bounded from above by a pressure-free boundary condition.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-05. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IscraC "HMEA").

References

- [1] Hildebrand, J.A., 2009. Anthropogenic and natural sources of ambient noise in the ocean. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 395, pp.5-20.
- [2] Chern, A., 2019. A reflectionless discrete perfectly matched layer. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 381, pp.91-109.
- [3] Sturm, F., 2005. Numerical study of broadband sound pulse propagation in three-dimensional oceanic waveguides. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 117(3), pp.1058-1079.
- [4] Porter, M.B., 2019. Beam tracing for two-and three-dimensional problems in ocean acoustics. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 146(3), pp.2016-2029.

Biogeochemical dynamics of the Mediterranean Sea in the future climate scenarios

Reale, M.^{1,2}, Cossarini, G.¹, Lazzari, P.¹, Lovato, T.³, Bolzon, G.¹, Solidoro, C.¹, Masina, S.³, Salon, S.¹

¹ National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics – OGS, Italy

²Earth System Physics Section, International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP), Trieste, Italy

³Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) Foundation, Bologna, Italy

Keywords: Mediterranean Sea, climate change, oligotrophy, deoxygenation, acidification

The Mediterranean Sea is a semi-enclosed basin located at the mid-latitudes which is widely recognized as a hot-spot for climate change (Giorgi, 2006). If the impacts of the increasing concentration of greenhouse gases on the dynamics of the basin has been investigated in many studies based single or multi-models' approach (Soto-Navarro et al., 2020), only a few studies so far have investigated the impacts of climate change on the biogeochemistry of the basin.

In this work we analysed the biogeochemical dynamics of the Mediterranean basin at the end of 21st century using high resolution projections of the physics under emissions scenario RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. The biogeochemical projections are based on the offline coupling between the physical model MFS16 and the transport reaction model OGSTM-BFM.

The analysis of the projections for the basin has shown an overall warming of the water column and a weakening of the thermohaline circulation of the basin. Associated with these changes it has been observed an overall decrease of nutrient concentration at the surface, a huge deoxygenation in the water column, an increase of the net primary production and a decrease of the organic matter stock, phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass. Moreover, we observe a huge acidification of the water column associated with the absorption of atmospheric CO₂, which is accumulated as DIC more efficiently in the Eastern basin with respect the Western basin (Fig.1). All these signals are stronger in the RCP8.5 scenario.

The results of these studies are affected by some uncertainties resulting from boundary conditions (Gibraltar, river load and atmospheric deposition) and model choice that will be addressed in the future using Earth system models.

Fig.1 – Temporal evolution of pH in the first 100m in the period 2005-2029 (first column), 2040-2059 (second column) and 2075-2099 (third column) in the scenario RCP8.5 (first row), RCP4.5 (second row) and the control simulation (third row).

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2015-07. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IscraC “TRICYCLO”, ”DYBIO”, ”EMED18”, ”MEDCLIM18”).

References

Giorgi, F (2006). Climate change hot-spots. *Geophysical research letters*, 33(8)

Soto-Navarro, J., Jordá, G., Amores, A. *et al.* Evolution of Mediterranean Sea water properties under climate change scenarios in the Med-CORDEX ensemble.(2020) *Clim Dyn* 54, 2135–2165. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-019-05105-4>

Automatic GPS data processing on Galileo machine

Tunini, L., Magrin, A. and Zuliani, D.

National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics – OGS, Italy

Keywords: GPS, deformation, time-series, GNSS, tectonics

The Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) provide a globally extended dataset of primary importance for a wide range of applications in different fields, such as crustal deformation monitoring, topographic surveying, near surface processes studies, and also for geodynamic modelling purposes.

North-eastern Italy and Slovenia are areas of particular interest because of the interplay between Adria and Eurasia tectonic plates, which has consequences on regional tectonics and related seismicity. OGS contributed to the regional monitoring system by installing FReDNet, a geodetic network composed of 16 permanent GNSS stations, which continuously provides real-time data and daily and hourly RINEX files, accessible through a public ftp repository. Furthermore, in order to place the regional deformation in a broader tectonic context, data coming from other geodetic networks covering the northern Italy and surrounding areas (GNSS network Antonio Marussi, EUREF European Network, Veneto GPS network, Lombardia GPS network, Piemonte GPS network, and some stations from Austrian and Slovenia networks), are also considered in the processing procedure.

RINEX input data are processed using the GAMIT-GLOBK software package (Herring et al., 2018), which estimates the three-dimensional relative positions of ground stations and satellite orbits from phase data, as well as atmospheric zenith delays, and Earth orientation parameters (Fig. 1).

The main objectives of this work are: 1) to ensure the continuity of GNSS processing; 2) to perform quality data checks on the entire dataset within the time interval 2002-2020; 3) to ensure the reproducibility of results and 4) to optimize the processing procedure. Given the huge amount of GNSS data, we decide to resort to the computing resources of the CINECA cluster Galileo to accomplish the tasks.

The first step has been the standardization of the processing procedure through the optimization of the shell scripts used in the data elaboration, the development of new scripts and the re-organization of data structure architecture on the Galileo machine. Particular attention has been paid to the data quality check, not only in the RINEX input files and in the final time series, but also in all the intermediate processing products.

In order to ensure the reproducibility of the results, a file version control program (Git) has been used to keep track of the changes in the different input files used by GAMIT-GLOBK to process GNSS data, as well as in the scripts used in the elaboration.

New scripts have been created to perform a day-by-day processing of GNSS data which allows proceeding from the download of input data (from different repositories) to the positioning of each single station without the intervention of any operator. The procedure has been tested on the Galileo cluster, and it is currently running on a local machine. Furthermore, through the implementation of fast broadcasted orbits in the processing, the day-by-day procedure allows to daily provide two kinds of solution: 1) final time series obtained using final and precise broadcasted orbits with a latency period of 29 days (i.e.: last day processed corresponds to 29 days before the current date); 2) preliminary time series for the last month period, where the most recent position is relative to just 3 days before the current date.

Since the performed tests and checks have revealed some errors and discrepancies in the previously obtained solutions and time series, we finally used the Galileo computing resources to re-process the entire GNSS dataset with an updated version of the GAMIT-GLOBK software, in order to have an up-to-date revised solution, well aligned with previous studies in the area.

In conclusion, HPC resources have been crucial to elaborate decades of data logged by hundreds of stations deployed in, and near, the Italian North-East area, and Galileo cluster has shown to be a great support to robustly evaluate the GNSS position and velocity fields in a short time.

Fig.1 - Flow chart of the GNSS processing procedure using GAMIT-GLOBK software on Galileo cluster.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-11. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IsraC IsC83_GPSIT).

References

Herring, T.A. and King, R., Floyd, M.A. and McClusky, S. C. (2018). GAMIT Reference Manual: GPS Analysis at MIT, Release 10.7. Department of Earth. Tech. rep., Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Mass. URL: <http://geoweb.mit.edu/gg/Intro_GG.pdf>

Evaluation of topographic effects on land and marine gravity data: A case study of the Gulf of Manfredonia and the North Adriatic region

Zampa, L. S.

National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics – OGS, Italy

Keywords: gravity data, python, digital-topographic-bathymetric-models

The gravity method used in geophysics has the important goal of locating density heterogeneities in the sub-surface. This is achieved by removing from the measurements points the gravity effect of a reference model approximating all the known masses composing the Earth. The approximation includes topography, oceans, seas, and eventually lakes, which gravitational attraction is generally defined as the topographic effect. The computation of this effect requires a detailed and extended collection of digital terrain and bathymetric models.

Our project is an attempt to create a semi-automatic python tool to efficiently estimate topographic effects for different gravity datatypes (land-based, marine, and sea-bottom gravity), integrating the best digital-models available.

The tool reads gravity data acquired on specific areas and integrates all the digital models covering the same areas and the nearby regions. As a result of the integration, the tool generates two different digital-topographic-bathymetric-models (DTBM), i.e., two raster files with different resolution and geographic limits. The first raster is a high-resolution DTBM used to approximate the topography close to the computational points, whether the second raster is a low-resolution DTBM used to approximate topography far from the computational points. The separation of low- and high-resolution areas is necessary to reduce the CPU time. The high-resolution grid is projected in a cartesian reference system and its gravity effect is calculated by discretizing the model into 3D prisms, for which the gravity effect is analytically defined. The low-resolution grid is considered starting at the distance from the computational point where the gravity caused by the Earth curvature becomes higher than the gravity data accuracy, and it is extended up to the distance where the gravity effect of the average elevation becomes lower than the gravity data accuracy. The gravity of the low-resolution DTBM is computed numerically using tesseroids, i.e., spherical prisms which takes into account the effects of Earth curvature. The sum of the effects calculated for the low- and high-resolution areas gives the complete topographic effect and the process is repeated on every measurement point.

Each element of the DTBMs (prisms or tesseroids) is associated with a specific density, which, in the simplest approximation, are the average crustal density, 2670 kg/m^3 , and the average sea-water density, 1030 kg/m^3 . The exact separation between land and sea-water elements is automatically done using vector polygons extracted from detailed coastlines databases (e.g., the Global Self-consistent, Hierarchical, High-resolution Geography Database, GSHHG). Moreover, gravity stations located at the sea-bottom uses an additional correction to evaluate the effect of water masses above the stations (which is different from the case of data points above the sea-surface).

This workflow has been tested on two different areas: the first is the Gulf of Manfredonia (southern Adriatic Sea), where we use a collection of sea-bottom and sea-surface satellite-altimeter gravity data, and the second is the Northeast Adriatic region where we used all sea-bottom, sea-surface, and terrestrial gravity data. The accuracy of the computation was confirmed by comparing our results with already established procedures in Fortran. One of the major problems of our workflow is the computational time, which increases (1) linearly with the number of input gravity data points and (2) exponentially with the resolution of the DTBMs. Improvements have been achieved using a simple parallelization scheme with the multiprocessing package of python.

Figure 1. (a) Digital-topographic-bathymetric model (DTBM) of the Northeast Adriatic region which integrates high-resolution and low-resolution bathymetric and topographic data; (b) gravity effect of the DTBM model calculated over points homogeneously distributed inside the red rectangle imaged on (a).

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2018-03.